

Towards Data-driven Spatial Justice: Identifying Walking-inaccessible Grocery Zones for Technologically Disadvantaged Groups in Dortmund

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Abstract. This study analyzes walking-accessibility to stationary grocery retailers for technologically disadvantaged groups (TDG) in Dortmund, Germany. As e-grocery platforms expand, populations facing barriers to digital adoption, whether due to age, migration-related barriers, or economic vulnerability, face a dual-exclusion risk: limited access to online platforms combined with a thinning physical retail network. TDGs are operationalized through three socio-demographic dimensions using z-score standardized indicators at the district level. Local Moran's I identifies statistically significant spatial concentration zones. Network-based service-area analysis evaluates walking-accessibility at 500 m, 700 m, and 1,000 m thresholds around full-range supermarkets and discounters. The findings reveal persistent inaccessible zones on the outskirts of the elderly and fragmented supply in economically disadvantaged inner-city districts.

Submission Type. Analysis; case study.

BoK Concepts. [AM11] Network Analysis; [AM8] Geo statistics; [GS3] Use of geospatial information Infrastructure.

Keywords. technologically disadvantaged groups; walking-accessibility; e-grocery; food security; spatial justice

1 Introduction

The digitalization of grocery retail is reshaping food procurement across Europe. In Germany, FMCG e-commerce grew by 30% year-on-year (HDE – Handelsverband Deutschland, 2022), yet digital adoption remains uneven. Persistent barriers related to age, language, income, and digital literacy create *non-liners* who depend entirely on stationary grocery retail (DIVSI,

2016). Simultaneously, the stationary outlet network declined by 31.6% between 2006 and 2022 (Statista, 2022). This dual trend raises spatial-justice concerns for populations unable to access e-grocery platforms (FAO, 1996; Cummins et al., 2008).

Dortmund (population ~615,000) exhibits a differentiated socio-spatial structure: ageing peripheral districts, central areas with higher shares of migration and economic vulnerability. This study investigates: (1) Where are TDG spatially concentrated? (2) What is the quality of walking-accessibility to stationary grocery retailers in these zones? (3) Which districts exhibit TDG walking-inaccessible zones requiring intervention?

2 Methodology

2.1 Study area and data

Dortmund is subdivided into statistical districts. The TDG are operationalized using five district-level indicators grouped into three dimensions: Age (share of residents aged ≥ 65 ; share of older single-person households), Migration (share of non-German population), and Economic (unemployment rate; share of transfer recipients, e.g., SGB II). Grocery outlet locations (full-range supermarkets and discounters) are compiled from municipal registers and OpenStreetMap and validated against aerial imagery.

2.2 Composite indicator and spatial clustering

All indicators are z-score standardized (Nardo et al., 2005). For each dimension, a composite score is calculated as the arithmetic mean of its standardized indicators. Local Moran's I (LISA) with queen-contiguity weights identifies

High–High (HH) TDG concentration zones (Anselin, 1995). The full methodology is summarised in Figure 1.

2.3 Walking-accessibility analysis

A pedestrian network derived from OpenStreetMap and municipal geodata supports service-area delineation at 500 m, 700 m, and 1,000 m around each grocery outlet (ArcGIS Pro Network Analyst). The TDG walking-inaccessible zones are defined as residential areas within HH clusters lacking 700 m grocery coverage (Klein et al., 2013).

2.4 Data and Software Availability

Socio-economic district-level indicators were sourced from the Dortmund Open Data portal (<https://open-data.dortmund.de>). District boundary geometries, the pedestrian street network, and grocery outlet locations were obtained from OpenStreetMap (accessed via QuickOSM) and from the municipal open geodata repository of the City of Dortmund (https://geoweb1.digistadtdo.de/doris_gdi/opengeodata/); outlet data were subsequently validated against aerial imagery. Spatial processing and network analysis were performed using QGIS and ArcGIS Pro (Network Analyst extension), while spatial autocorrelation statistics were computed in R using the *sf* and *spdep* packages. Aggregated district-level results and modular processing scripts are available from the authors upon request.

3 Results and Discussion

The final result of this study is illustrated in Figure 2. The results reveal a spatial clustering of technologically disadvantaged groups in specific districts of Dortmund. Areas with higher concentrations of elderly residents and economically vulnerable populations show notably low walking-accessibility to grocery retailers, creating an exclusion phenomenon where populations unable to adopt digital shopping technologies face the greatest physical accessibility barriers.

In elderly-dominated peripheral districts, walking-inaccessible zones persist despite moderate population density. These areas are characterized by retail consolidation toward city centers, forcing elderly and mobility-limited residents to undertake longer journeys or depend on social networks for essential supplies.

Economically disadvantaged inner-city districts exhibit fragmented retail supply, with pockets of severe inaccessibility despite a higher concentration of discount retailers. The absence of full-range supermarkets in these areas limits food choice and nutritional diversity, compounding existing inequalities.

These findings reveal a dual-exclusion dynamic: The TDG lack access to e-grocery platforms while the physical retail network thins in their concentration zones.

4 Conclusions

This study operationalizes TDG walking-inaccessibility by combining multi-dimensional socio-demographic profiling, spatial autocorrelation, and network-based service-area analysis within a reproducible GIS workflow. Applied to Dortmund, the approach reveals spatial justice disparities that aggregate metrics often overlook, with the highest concentrations of technologically disadvantaged groups coinciding with the weak pedestrian-accessible grocery coverage. These areas represent priority zones for planning interventions, including targeted retail provision and mobility support measures. However, the planning applicability of the results is strongly dependent on the spatial resolution of openly available data from the City of Dortmund. The use of district-level aggregates may obscure fine-grained accessibility patterns; access to higher-resolution demographic and population data at the city block or parcel level would substantially improve the identification of TDG locations and provide more precise insights into their walking accessibility. The methodology is transferable to other urban contexts and provides a foundation for future research incorporating temporal dynamics and qualitative perspectives on accessibility.

Declaration of Generative AI in Writing

Generative AI tools were used exclusively for language editing and structural refinement. All scientific content, methodology, analysis, and interpretations remain the responsibility of the authors.

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References

- Anselin, L.: Local Indicators of Spatial Association—LISA, *Geographical Analysis*, 27, 93–115, <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1538-4632.1995.tb00338.x>, 1995.
- Cummins, S., Findlay, A., Higgins, C., Petticrew, M., Sparks, L., and Thomson, H.: Reducing inequalities in health and diet: findings from a study on the impact of a food retail development, *Environment and Planning A*, 40, 402–422, <https://doi.org/10.1068/a38371>, 2008.
- DIVSI: DIVSI Ü60-Studie: Die digitalen Lebenswelten der über 60-Jährigen in Deutschland, <https://www.divsi.de/>

[wp-content/uploads/2016/10/DIVSI-UE60-Studie.pdf](#),
hamburg, 2016.

FAO: Rome Declaration on World Food Security, <https://www.fao.org/3/w3613e/w3613e00.htm>, world Food Summit, Rome, 13–17 November 1996, 1996.

HDE – Handelsverband Deutschland: HDE Online-Monitor 2022, <https://einzelhandel.de/online-monitor>, 2022.

Klein, K., Krüger, T., Anders, S., Walther, M., and Segerer, M.: Qualifizierte Nahversorgung im Lebensmitteleinzelhandel, <https://einzelhandel.de/nahversorgungsstudie>, studie der Hafencity Universität Hamburg (HCU) und der IREIBS Universität Regensburg im Auftrag des HDE und BVL, 2013.

Nardo, M., Saisana, M., Saltelli, A., Tarantola, S., Hoffman, A., and Giovannini, E.: Handbook on Constructing Composite Indicators, <https://doi.org/10.1787/533411815016>, OECD Statistics Working Papers 2005/03, Paris, 2005.

Statista: Anzahl der Filialen im Lebensmittelhandel in Deutschland 2016–2022, <https://de.statista.com/statistik/daten/studie/157293/umfrage/anzahl-der-geschaefte-im-deutschen-einzelhandel-nach-geschaefstypen/>, statista Study ID 157293, 2022.

Figure 1. Methodology workflow: The TDG operationalization through composite indicator construction, spatial autocorrelation analysis, and walking-accessibility evaluation.

Figure 2. Spatial accessibility of stationary grocery retailers for technologically disadvantaged groups in Dortmund (2022). Three maps are combined: (*left*) districts identified through **spatial autocorrelation** as concentration zones of technologically disadvantaged groups; (*centre*) **walking accessibility zones** (500 m, 700 m, and 1,000 m) around grocery retailers overlaid on concentration zones, with store locations shown by chain; and (*right*) final **walking-inaccessible areas** within the identified concentration zones.